

EXISTENCE OF EIGENVALUES IN A DISCRETE THREE-PARTICLE MODEL OPERATOR

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Abstract. Present paper is devoted to the study of the essential and discrete spectrum of a model operator H_μ , where $\mu > 0$ is a coupling constant. It is associated with the system of three particles on the one-dimensional lattice. A model operator H_μ is considered as a linear, bounded and self-adjoint operator acting in the Hilbert space, consisting of the square-integrable symmetric functions defined on the two-dimensional torus T^2 . For all values of the coupling constant μ we prove the existence of the unique eigenvalue of the model operator H_μ .

Key words: model operator, particle, lattice, torus, coupling constant, essential spectrum, eigenvalue.

СУЩЕСТВОВАНИЕ СОБСТВЕННЫХ ЗНАЧЕНИЙ ДИСКРЕТНОГО МОДЕЛЬНОГО ТРЁХЧАСТИЧНОГО ОПЕРАТОРА

Аннотация. Настоящая работа посвящена исследованию существенного и дискретного спектра модельного оператора H_μ , где μ — константа связи. Данный оператор ассоциирован с системой трёх частиц на одномерной решётке. Модельный оператор H_μ рассматривается как линейный, ограниченный и самосопряжённый оператор, действующий в гильбертовом пространстве квадратично интегрируемых симметрических функций, заданных на двумерном торе T^2 . Для всех значений константы связи μ доказано существование единственного собственного значения модельного оператора H_μ .

Ключевые слова: модельный оператор, частица, решётка, тор, константа связи, существенный спектр, собственное значение.

One of the important issues in the spectral analysis of model operators associated with discrete Schrödinger operators is the study of eigenvalues lying outside the essential spectrum [1-11]. This work is devoted to the study of the essential spectrum and eigenvalues of one model operator associated with a system of three particles on a one-dimensional lattice.

Let $L_2^s(T^2)$ - the Hilbert space of square-integrable symmetric (complex-valued) functions defined on T^2 .

In the Hilbert space $L_2^s(T^2)$, consider the so-called discrete model operator H_μ acting by the formula

$$H_\mu = H_0 - \mu V_1 - \mu V_2, \quad (1)$$

where operators H_0 and V_α , $\alpha = 1, 2$, defined as

$$(H_0 f)(x, y) = (u(x) + u(y))f(x, y), \quad f \in L_2^s(T^2);$$

$$(V_1 f)(x, y) = \varphi(x) \int_{T^1} \varphi(t) f(t, y) dt, \quad f \in L_2^s(T^2);$$

$$(V_2 f)(x, y) = \varphi(y) \int_{T^1} \varphi(t) f(x, t) dt, \quad f \in L_2^s(T^2).$$

Moreover $u(\cdot)$ and $\varphi(\cdot)$ are the real values of the analytic functions on T^1 .

Under these assumptions the operator H_μ defined by formula (1) is bounded and self-adjoint in $L_2(T^2)$.

To formulate the main result of the work, along with the discrete model operator H_μ , we also consider the so-called Friedrichs model h_μ , acting in the Hilbert space $L_2(T^1)$ according to the formula

$$h_\mu := h_0 - \mu v,$$

where the operators h_0 and v are defined as

$$(h_0 g)(x) = u(x)g(x), \quad g \in L_2(T^1);$$

$$(vg)(x) = \varphi(y) \int_{T^1} \varphi(t)g(t)dt, \quad g \in L_2(T^1).$$

The Friedrichs model is also bounded and self-adjoint operators in Hilbert space $L_2(T^1)$.

Obviously, by definition of operators H_μ and h_μ model operator H_μ can be represented as tensor sum $H_\mu = h_\mu \otimes I + I \otimes h_\mu$. Here I stands for the single operator in $L_2(T^1)$.

In this paper, we will study the essential spectrum and eigenvalues of a discrete model operator H_μ using the tensor sum of operators.

The perturbation operator v of an operator h_0 is a self-adjoint operator of rank 1. According to the well-known Weyl theorem on the conservation of the essential spectrum under finite-dimensional perturbations, it follows that the essential spectrum $\sigma_{\text{ess}}(h_\mu)$ of an operator h_μ coincides with the essential spectrum of the operator h_0 .

It is known that, where the numbers and are determined by the equalities

It is known that $\sigma_{\text{ess}}(h_0) = [m, M]$, where the numbers m and M are determined by the equalities

$$m := \min_{x \in T^1} u(x), \quad M := \max_{x \in T^1} u(x).$$

From the last two facts it follows that $\sigma_{\text{ess}}(h_\mu) = [m, M]$

Everywhere we assume that the function $u(\cdot)$ has a minimum at the points $x_k \in T^1$, $k = \overline{1, n}$, where n is a natural number ($1 \leq n < \infty$). As such a function, we can take a function of the form

$$u(x) = 1 - \cos(3x).$$

Then the function $u(\cdot)$ has a minimum at the points

$$x_1 = 0, \quad x_2 = \frac{2\pi}{3}, \quad x_3 = -\frac{2\pi}{3}.$$

We describe the number and location of the eigenvalues of the Friedrichs model h_μ .

Lemma 1. a) If $v(x_k) \neq 0$, $k = \overline{1, n}$, then for all values of the interaction parameter $\mu > 0$ the Friedrichs model h_μ has a single eigenvalue E_μ lying to the left m .

b) For all values of the interaction parameter $\mu > 0$ the Friedrichs h_μ model has no eigenvalues lying to the right M .

Now let's formulate the main result of our work.

Theorem 1. a) Let $v(x_k) \neq 0$, $k = \overline{1, n}$. Then, for the essential spectrum of the operator H_μ equalities hold

$$\sigma_{\text{ess}}(H_\mu) = [2m, 2M] \cup [m + E_\mu, M + E_\mu].$$

In addition, for all values of the interaction parameter $\mu > 0$ the model operator H_μ has a single eigenvalue $2E_\mu$, i.e.

$$\sigma_{\text{disc}}(H_\mu) = \{2E_\mu\}, \text{ at that } E_\mu < m.$$

b) For all values of the interaction parameter $\mu > 0$ the model operator H_μ has no eigenvalues lying to the right $2M$.

In the proof of the Theorem 1, the key role is played by the Lemma 1 and tensor structure $H_\mu = h_\mu \otimes I + I \otimes h_\mu$ of operator H_μ .

Usually the sets $[m + E_\mu, M + E_\mu]$ and $[2m, 2M]$ are called, respectively, the two-particle and three-particle branches of the essential spectrum of the model operator H_μ .

It can also be shown that the spectrum of the operator $H_0 - \mu V_1$ coincides with the essential spectrum of the operator H_μ , i.e. $\sigma_{\text{ess}}(H_\mu) = \sigma(H_0 - \mu V_1)$. It can be seen that the operator $H_0 - \mu V_1$ has a simpler structure than H_μ .

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